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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0066-3547

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Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

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государственного медицинского университета.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

Абзалова Шахноза Рустамовна
кандидат медицинских наук, доцент, Ташкентский
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доктор медицинских наук, профессор, проректор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского
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Худоярова Дилдора Рахимовна

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Акушерства и гинекологии №1 Самаркандского
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ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5770-2255

Раббимова Дилфуза Таштемировна

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государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-4229-6017

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующий кафедрой
Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144

Ярмухамедова Саодат Хабибовна

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент, заведующая
кафедрой Пропедевтики внутренних болезней Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5975-1261

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

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хирургии Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2650-4445

Акбаров Миршавкат Миролимович

доктор медицинских наук,
Республиканский специализированный центр
хирургии имени академика В.Вахидова

Саидов Саидмир Абборович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский
фармацевтический институт
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428

Тураев Феруз Фатхуллаевич

доктор медицинских наук, главный научный с
отрудник отделения приобретенных пороков сердца
Республиканского специализированного центра
хирургии имени академика В.Вахидова.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6778-6920

Худанов Бахтинур Ойбутаевич

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Бабаджанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович

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медицинский институт, кафедра Дерматовенерология, детская
дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Факультетской
детской хирургии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии,
неонатологии и пропедевтики детских болезней №2
Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Эшкobilов Тура Жураевич

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Судебной
медицины и патологической анатомии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-3914-7221

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры
онкологии Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503

Верстка: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

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Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

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Doctor of Medical Sciences, Vice-Rector for scientific work
and Innovation, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Responsible secretary:

Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna
doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Responsible for publication:

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0066-3547

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ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5770-2255*

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*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Head of the Department of Propaedeutics of Pediatrics,
Samarkand State Medical University.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-4229-6017*

Oripov Firdavs Suratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Head of the Department of Histology, Cytology and
Embryology of Samarkand State Medical University.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Yarmukhamedova Saodat Khabibovna

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Head of the Department of Propaedeutics of Internal
Medicine, Samarkand State Medical University.
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5975-1261*

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*Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6778-6920*

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*Doctor of sciences in medicine, Tashkent Pediatric
Medical Institute, Department of Dermatovenerology,
pediatric dermatovenerology and AIDS
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
Faculty of Children Department of Surgery.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

Yuldashev Botir Akhmatovich

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
Pediatrics, Neonatology and Propaedeutics of Pediatrics,
Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Eshkobilov Tura Juraevich

*candidate of medical Sciences, associate Professor
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anatomy of the Samarkand state medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-3914-7221*

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ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

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TODJIYEVA Nigina Iskandarovna
Samarkand State Medical University

HYPERPLASTIC PROCESSES OF ENDOMETRIUM IN PREMENOPAUSE: IMPROVEMENT OF TREATMENT METHODS

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ANNOTATION

The purpose of the study: to improve the methods of treatment of hyperplastic processes of the endometrium.

Materials and methods: the object of the study were 40 women with hyperplastic processes and 20 control group of healthy women who underwent a complete clinical and laboratory examination with a biopsy and subsequent treatment.

Results: in the course of the study, the efficacy of treatment with Median in premenopausal women was studied, and therapeutic efficacy was found when using the drug for more than 6 cycles.

Conclusion: Long-term administration of Median is effective and prevents relapses.

Keywords: hyperplastic processes of the endometrium, premenopause, combined oral contraceptives, premenstrual syndrome, treatment methods.

ТОДЖИЕВА Нигина Искандаровна

Самаркандский Государственный медицинский университет

ГИПЕРПЛАСТИЧЕСКИЕ ПРОЦЕССЫ ЭНДОМЕТРИЯ В ПРЕМЕНОПАУЗАЛЬНОМ ПЕРИОДЕ: СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДОВ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Цель исследования: совершенствование методов лечения гиперпластических процессов эндометрия.

Материалы и методы: объектом исследования явились 40 женщин с гиперпластическими процессами и 20 контрольная группа здоровых женщин, которым проведено полное клинико-лабораторное обследование с биопсией и с последующим лечением.

Результаты: в ходе исследования изучено эффективность лечения препаратом Медиа у женщин пременопаузального возраста, выявлено терапевтическая эффективность при применении препарата более 6 циклов.

Заключение: препарата Медиа в пролонгированном приеме является эффективным и предупреждает рецидивы.

Ключевые слова: гиперпластические процессы эндометрия, пременопауза, комбинированные оральные контрацептивы, предменструальный синдром, методы лечения

TODJIYEVA Nigina Iskandarovna
Samarkand Davlat tibbiyot universiteti

PREMENOPAUZAL DAVRDAGI ENDOMETRIYNING GIPERPLASTIK JARAYONLARI: DAVOLASH USULLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Tadqiqot maqsadi: endometriyning giperplastik jarayonlarini davolash usullarini takomillashtirish.

Materiallar va usullar: tadqiqot obyekti giperplastik jarayonlari bo'lgan 40 nafar ayol hamda 20 nafar nazorat guruhidagi sog'lom ayollar bo'lib, ular to'liq klinik va laboratoriya tekshiruvlaridan, biopsiya va keyingi davolashdan o'tkazilishgan.

Natijalar: tadqiqot davomida premenopauzal yoshdagi ayollarda Mediana preparati bilan davolash samaradorligi o'rganildi va preparat 6 sikldan ko'proq foydalanilganda terapevtik samaradorligi aniqlandi.

Xulosa: Medianning uzoq muddatli qo'llanilishi samarali va qaytalanishlarning oldini oladi.

Kalit so'zlar: endometriy giperplastik jarayonlari, premenopauza, aralash og'iz kontratseptivlari, premenstrual sindrom, davolash usullari.

Kirish. Endometriy giperplaziyasi (EG) bachadon shilliq qavati patologiyasining eng keng tarqalgan shakli bo'lib, u endometriyning fiziologik bo'lmagan proliferatsiyasi sifatida kuzatiladi, bu bezlar va to'qimalarning stromal tarkibiy qismlarining qayta tuzilishi bilan birga keladi. Endometriydagi giperplastik jarayonlarning mexanizmlari haligacha yaxshi tushunilmagan, bu esa ushbu patologiyaga ega bemorlarni patogenez jihatidan asoslangan davolash tizimini ishlab chiqishni qiyinlashtiradi [5, 8, 11, 17].

Umumiy nuqtai nazarga ko'ra, EG rivojlanishida yetakchi rol progesteron ta'sirining yetishmasligi bilan birga haddan tashqari estrogenik stimulyatsiyaga tegishli. Garchi bu fikrdan tashqari boshqa yangi faktlar mavjud bo'lsa-da, estrogenik kontseptsiya hali ham yetakchi rolda qolmoqda [1, 3, 15].

EGning atipiyasiz shaklini davolash usullaridan eng keng tarqalgani bu gormonlarni almashtirish terapiyasini o'tkazishdir [7, 10, 12]. Bir qator tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, gormonal terapiyaning atipiyasiz EG da samaradorligi past ya'ni 42% gacha [3, b.1755]. Boshqalar fikriga ko'ra, EG ning qaytalanishi faqat gormonal terapiya bilan davolangan ayollarning 26 foizida aniqlanadi [9, b.305; 12, 357-bet]. Gormonal preparatlarni buyurishdan oldin endometriyning gistologik tekshiruvini o'tkaziladi.

Hozirgi vaqtda shifokorlar arsenalida EGni davolash uchun keng turdagi mahsulotlar mavjud. Ularga progestin, aralash og'iz kontratseptivlari (AOKlar), antigonadotrop dorilar, GnRG agonistlari kiradi. Gormon terapiyasining samaradorligi hozirgacha ancha yuqoriligicha qolmoqda. Bir qancha mualliflarning fikricha [2, 4, 6, 11, 18], gormon terapiyasi bilan davolangan bemorlarda umumiy endometriy giperplaziyasining (UEG) qaytalanishi 26 %da va bu terapiyasiz davolangan ayollarning 72,1 % da kuzatilgan.

So'nggi yillarda tobora ko'proq odamlar minimal yon ta'sirga ega bo'lgan davolanishni izlashmoqda. Uzoq tarixga ega ya'ni 50 yildan ortiq foydalanib kelingan AOKdan foydalanish, ayniqsa uning so'nggi avlodlarini nafaqat ularning yuqori terapevtik samaradorligini, balki boshqa

ijobiy ta'sirlarni ham aks ettiradi. Ma'lumki, 12 oy davomida AOKlaridan foydalanish endometriy saratoni xavfini 50% ga kamaytiradi [5, 6, 10, 11, 16].

Xuddi shu himoya ta'siri endometriy saratonining xavf guruhidagi yuqori ayollarda maksimal darajada va barcha asosiy gistologik turlariga keng qo'llaniladi.

AOKlar ta'sirida endometriyning proliferativ fazasi tez regressiyaga uchraydi, uning ichida bezlarning erta sekretor transformatsiyasi nomoyon bo'ladi va stromada bargli transformatsiya kuzatiladi [8, 12, 14]. Avvalo, regressiya jarayonlari bezli komponent bilan bog'liq, shuning uchun stroma va bez komponentlari nisbatida stromaning nisbiy miqdori ustunlik qiladi. Endometriydagi qon tomirlar sezilarli o'zgarishlarga duchor bo'ladi: spiral arteriolalarning rivojlanishiga qarshi harakat sodir bo'ladi va ularning o'rniga kapillyarlarning keng tarmog'i bachadon tanasining shilliq qavatining sirt qatlamlarini hosil qiladi [10, 15, 17].

Tadqiqot maqsadi: endometriyning giperplastik jarayonlarini premenopauzal davrdagi ayollarda davolash usullarini takomillashtirish.

Tadqiqot materiallari va metodlari. Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universitetining 1-sonli klinikasiga 2020-2022 yillarda ginekologiya bo'limiga murojaat qilgan ayollardan 40 nafar endometriy giperplaziyasi bo'lgan ayollar asosiy guruh sifatida tadqiqot obyektini tashkil qilishdi. Nazorat guruhiga 20 nafar deyarli sog'lom hisoblangan ayollar kirgizildi. Asosiy guruh bemorlarining o'rtacha yoshi $44,8 \pm 2,76$, nazorat guruhi bemorlariniki esa - $45,7 \pm 1,66$ edi, bu tekshirilgan ayollar guruhida yosh bo'yicha taqqoslashda o'zgarishlar yo'qligidan dalolat beradi.

Premenopauzal davrda endometriyning giperplastik jarayonlari bilan hastalangan 40 nafar bemor kompleks klinik-laborator tekshiruvdan o'tkazildi: umumiy klinik tekshiruv, obyektiv va ginekologik tekshiruv, labarot tadqiqotlardan umumiy qon tahlili, umumiy peshob tahlili, qonning biokimyoviy tahlili, qindan olingan surtma tahlili, gormonlar tahlili, instrumental usullardan UTT va endometriyning biopsiyasi. Endometriy giperplastik jarayonlari bilan kasallangan bemorlarni patomorfologik tekshirish natijalarini olgandan so'ng, uzoq muddatli past dozada monofazali aralash og'iz kontratseptiv (AOK)laridan "Mediana" preparati buyurildi. Bemorlar bir yil preparat qabul qilishi davomida kuzatildi. Bu vaqt oralig'ida klinik va laboratoriya tadqiqot natijalari monitoringi ta'minlandi, bemorlarning tana vazni dinamikasi baholandi. Mediana preparatini qabul qilish 6 oy davom etganidan so'ng bachadon shilliq qavatining holati yana morfologik nazoratdan o'tkazildi. Endometriy qalinligining exografik nazorati UTT yordamida har 3, 6 va 12 oydan keyin amalga oshirildi.

Nazorat guruhida ayollarga ham asosiy guruhga buyurilgan tadqiqot usullari amalga oshirildi. Ushbu bemorlarga endometriy biopsiyasi uning patologiyasini istisno qilish uchun o'tkazildi.

Olingan barcha natijalar ularning o'rtacha qiymati (M) va o'rtacha og'ish ko'rsatkichida (m) hisoblangan. Olingan ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish uchun quyidagi statistik ishlov berish usullaridan foydalanildi: t - Student mezoni, Pirson korrelyatsiya tahlili.

Ma'lumotlar bazasi Microsoft Office 2013 dasturida bashorat qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan mezonlar va barcha mumkin bo'lgan diagnostika funktsiyalari asosida tuzilgan. Barcha hisob-kitoblar Excel dasturining statistik funksiyasi va Statistic 6.0 dan foydalangan holda amalga oshirildi.

Tadqiqot natijalari. Baemorlar shikoyatlari tahlil qilinganda davolanishdan oldin menorragiya (57.5%) va metroragiya (42.5%) ko'rsatkichi baland bo'lgan. Qorinning pastki qismida og'riqqa 37.5% ayollar shikoyat qilgan. Vazomotor va emotsional vegetative alomatlar 7.5% da uchragan. Nazorat guruhi ayollarida hech qanday shikoyat aniqlangamagan.

Asosiy guruh bemorlarining shikoyatlari dinamikasi 1-jadvalda va 1-rasmda aks ettirilgan.

Jadval 1

Bemorlarning gormonal terapiya jarayonidan oldingi va terapiya davomidagi asosiy shikoyatlari.

Shikoyatlar	Davolanishdan oldin	6 oy davolanishdan so'ng

	n	%	n	%
Menorragiya	23	57.5	2	5
Metrorragiya	17	42.5	-	-
Qorinning pastki qismida og'riq	15	37.5	-	-
Hayz ko'rishdan oldin va keyin ajralmalar kelishi	11	27.5	4	10
Oligomenoreya	5	12.5	25	62.5
Amenoreya	-	-	7	17.5
Vazomotor va emotsional-vegetativ alomatlar	3	7.5	-	-

Jadvaldan ko'rinib turibdiki OAKning Mediana preparatini 6 oy qabul qilishdan keyin, 25 (62,5%) nafar bemorda oligomenoreya aniqlangan ya'ni bachadondan qon ketish holatlari butkul to'xtatilgan. Yil oxirida tekshirilgan bemorlarning 34 nafarida (85,0%) oligomenoreya aniqlangan. Bundan tashqari, tadqiqot davomida PMS belgilarini yo'q qilishda ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi aniq bo'ldi, bu esa EG bo'lgan ayollarda hayot sifatini yaxshilanishiga olib keladi. PMS nomoyon bo'ladigan 30 (75%) nafar ayollarda ko'rsatilgan terapiyada ijobiy natijalar kuzatilib, hayot sifatining yaxshilanishiga erishildi.

Rasm 1

Bemorlarda terapiya kursining boshlanishidan 6 oy o'tgach, hayz ko'rish deyarli barcha bemorlarda to'xtatilgan, faqat 1 ta (2,5%) bemorda hayz ko'rish 3-4 kunlik shaklda kam miqdorda saqlanib qolgan; Qorinning pastki qismidagi og'riqlardan shikoyat qiladigan bemorlar kamroq bo'lgan, bu hayz ko'rish sikli bilan bog'liq deb tahmin qilishimiz mumkin. Chunki 6 oylik davodan so'ng ushbu shikoyat bironta ayolda uchramagan. Terapiya tugagandan so'ng, hayz ko'rish davrida oz miqdorda shilliq jigarrang ajralmalar kelishini 12.5% ayollar qayd etishgan.

EG bilan xastalangan bemorning bachadon bo'shlig'idan qirindini gistologik tekshirish paytida barcha holatlarda atipiyasiz endometriy giperplaziya aniqlangan shundan 21 (52,5%) bemorlarda umumiy tipik endometriy giperplaziyasi, 19 (47,5%) bemorlarda og'ir tipik endometriy giperplaziya mavjud. Nazorat guruhida endometriy giperplaziyasi aniqlanmagan.

Barchamizga ayon xalqimiz ichida gormonal preparatlar qabul qilish vazn oshishiga olib keladi degan fikr mavjud. Ushbu fikr tufayli ham ko'plab ayollar davolanishmaydi yoki davolanishni oxirigacha olib borishmaydi. Mediana preparatini qabul qilish davomida biz asosiy guruh ayollarining tana vaznini nazorat qildik. Tadqiqot shuni korsatdiki to'g'ri ovqatlanish qoidalariga rioya qilgan holda ayollar kunlik vazifalarini bajarishganda tana vazni kamayishi va yanada barqarorlashishi kuzatildi.

Preparatni qabul qilishning taxminan 3-oyligida (27-35 kun oralig'ida) bemorning 42.5%da tana vaznining 0,5 kg gacha kamayishi kuzatildi, 6 oy davomida uzluksiz dori-darmonlarni qabul qilganidan keyin esa tana vaznining pasayishi 32.5% ayollarda 1-2 kg gacha tashkil qildi. Ushbu natija bir yil davomida saqlanib keldi. Jismoniy mehnat bilan shug'ullangan ayollarda esa tana vazni 3-5 kg gacha kamaydi. Shuni takidlash kerakki, 17.5% kamharakat va jismoniy mehnat bilan umuman shug'ullanmaydigan ayollarda tana vazni yil davomida 3 kg gacha ortdi.

Ushbu ma'lumotlardan xulosa qilishimiz mumkinki, AOK lari tana vazniga to'g'ridan to'g'ri ta'sir ko'rsatishmaydi. Odatiy hayot tarzida AOKlar tana vazni barqaroq saqlanib qolishiga yoki 1-2 kg kamayishiga olib keladi. Lekin to'g'ri ovqatlanish qoidalariga rioya qilinmasa, hayot tarzi o'troqshaklda bo'lsa tana vazni oshishi kuzatiladi.

Mediana tarkibiga kiruvchi Drospirononning antimineralokortikoid ta'sirining qo'shimcha natijalari qon bosimining barqarorligi edi. Mediana preparatini qabul qilishda qon bosimini dinamik nazorat qilish, davolashni boshlashdan oldin barqaror gipertenziyasi bo'lgan 17 (42.5%) kishi bo'lgan. Shundan 9tasida (52.9% ushbu bemorlar ichida, 22.5% umumiy asosiy guruh bemorlari ichida) AQB barqarorlashishi tendentsiyasi aniqlangan.

Bemorni davolashdan oldin va keyin o'tkazilgan UTT da bachadonning endometriy qavati qalinligini exografik holatiga alohida e'tibor qaratdik. Tekshirilayotgan bemorlarning asosiy guruhida o'rtacha terapiya boshlangan paytdan boshlab 3 oydan o'tgandan keyin endometriyning yupqalashishi $2,39 \pm 1,13$ mm ni tashkil etdi, bu natijalarni ishonchli tarzda davolash samaradorligini ko'rsatdi. Ya'ni endometriyning qalinligi 3 oy davodan keyin o'rytacha $10,1 \pm 1,88$ mm ni tashkil etdi.

Terapiya tugagandan so'ng o'tkaziladigan ultra tovush tekshiruvida bachadon shilliq qavatining giperplastik jarayonining exoskopik belgilari aniqlanmadi. Gormonal terapiyani qabul qilgan bemorlar asosiy davo (1 yil mobaynida Mediana preparatini qabul qilishi) tugagandan keyin 30-35 kun davomida nazoratda bo'lishdi. Ularda endometriy qalinligining o'rtacha ko'rsatkichlari $6,11 \pm 1,38$ mm ni tashkil etdi (2-jadval).

Jadval 2

Terapiyadan oldingi va keying UTT ma'lumotlari

Natijalar	Davolanishdan oldin	3 oy davolanishdan so'ng	6 oy davolanishdan so'ng
M-exo, mm	8,1+0,9	2,39 ± 1,13	3,99 ± 0,75
Tuxumdonlar hajmi sm ³	12,4±0,5	7,4+0,1	8,9+0,3
Endometrium qalinligi, mm	18,1+0,9	10,1 ± 1,88	6,11 ± 1,38

Terapiya ta'sirini baholash uchun Mediana preparati qo'llanilgandan 6 oydan keyin endometriy biopsiyasi tadqiqot uchun olingan endometriy to'qimalari namunalarining gistologik tekshiruvini barcha asosiy guruh ayollarida o'tkazildi.

Aniqlanishicha, preparatni qabul qilishdan 6 oy o'tib 36 (90%) nafar bemorlarda endometriy giperplaziyasining morfologik belgilari umuman aniqlanmagan, faqat 10% ayollarda endometriy giperplaziyasi o'chog'lari aniqlangan.

Menorargiya bo'yicha qolgan shikoyatlarni hisobga olgan holda, 52 yoshli EG bilan og'rigan 1 (2.5%) nafar bemorda davolash samarali emas deb baholangan.

Davolanish boshlanganidan 6 oy o'tgach, endometriyning takroriy biopsiyasi o'tkazilganda, mavjud morfologik turdagi EG rivojlanishini aniqlansa ularga jarrohlik davo usulini qo'llash () va so'ngra yana gormonal terapiyadan foydalanish tavsiya etilgan. Agar biopsiya natijasida giperplaziya

malignizatsiyasi belgilari aniqlansa darhol bachadon eksterpatsiyasi masalasi hamda onkologik dispanser kuzatuvini tavsiya etilgan.

Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, biz jiddiy salbiy ta'sirlarni va ishlatilgan terapiyaning intoleransiyasini topmadik. Ko'pgina bemorlarda gormonal dorilarni qabul qilish ijobiy kechdi. Gormonal terapiyaning salbiy ta'siri orasida kuchli qon ketishi qayd etilgan. Medianani qabul qilish to'xtatilganda 6 nafar bemorlarda (15%) ushbu salbiy ta'sir qayd etilgan. Qon ketishning bu davomiyligi bunda $4,9 \pm 0,2$ kunni tashkil qilgan. Ko'pincha yo'qotilgan qon miqdori kam edi, shuning uchun terapiya davom ettirilgan va ushbu nojo'ya ta'sir bartaraf etilgan.

Terapiya tugaganidan keyin 3 oy ichida 82,1% bemorlarda qiyosiy morfologik (endometriyning bezli giperplaziyasining yo'qolishi) va klinik (hayz siklini normallasishi) ta'sirining tezligi qayd etildi.

Terapiya tugagandan so'ng uni baholash maqsadida 17 (42.5%) bemorga alohida diagnostik qirish orqali material olish o'tkazildi, 23 (57.5%) holatda bachadon bo'shlig'ining aspiratsiyasi o'tkazildi. Bachadon bo'shlig'ini tirnash paytida olingan endometriy qalinligi 15 (37.5%) holatda o'rtacha, 2 (5%) holatda kam deb baholanadi.

Terapiyaning samaradorligini baholash uchun endometriyning gistologik tekshiruvini o'tkazildi. Gormonal terapiya o'tkazilgan bemorlar guruhida olingan materialning morfologik ko'rinish quyidagicha bo'ldi: 36 (90%) holatda endometriy atrofiyasi kuzatildi, 4 (10%) nafarda esa endometriy proliferatsiya bosqichining dastlabki bosqichidagi holatga o'xshash holatda edi.

Xulosalar. Tadqiqot natijasida biz quyidagi xulosalarga keldik:

1. Ayollarning premenopauzal davrida EGning asosiy klinik ko'rinishlari quyidagicha nomoyon bo'ladi: menorragiya (57.5%) va metroragiya (42.5%), qorinning pastki qismida og'riq (37,5%), hayzdan oldin va keyingi ajralmalar kelishi (27,5%), vazomotor va emotsional vegetativ belgilar (7.5%).

2. EG bilan xastalangan bemorning bachadon bo'shlig'idan qirindini gistologik tekshirish paytida barcha holatlarda atipiyasiz endometriy giperplaziya aniqlangan shundan 21 (52,5%) bemorlarda umumiy tipik endometriy giperplaziyasi, 19 (47,5%) bemorlarda og'ir tipik endometriy giperplaziya mavjud.

3. EG bilan og'riq bemorlarga Mediana AOK dori-darmonlarini uzoq muddat (1 yil) davomidada qabul qilishganda terapevtik ta'sir ko'rsatishning samarali va klinik qaytalanishlarni oldini olishi aniqlangan.

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